

Evaluation of rice cultivars for yellow stem borer (YSB) resistance

M. M. Mahar and I. M. Bhatti, Rice Research Institute, Dokri, Sind, Pakistan

We screened 44 rice cultivars for field resistance to YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas* Walker in 1983-84. On 27 Jul, 37-d-old seedlings were transplanted in 3- × 1.5-m subplots at 20- × 20-cm spacing. There were 7 rows and 15 plants/row for each entry. Deadhearts were counted 55 d after transplanting and whiteheads just before harvest. Infestation was scored,

Reaction of rice cultivars to YSB, Sind, Pakistan.

Cultivar	Deadheart score	Whitehead score
B441-B-126-3-2-1	5	7
B2850-B-SI-2-3	7	7
IR13635-8	3	9
IR13635-45	1	7
IR13639-34	1	3
IR13639-37	1	7
IR13641-33	1	9
IR19632-174	1	7
IR19362-183	5	9
AusBalam	3	7
RNR74802	1	7
IR1552	3	7
UPR103-44-2	1	9
Chianung Sen Yu 23	3	9
IR19782-2-3-3	1	5
CO21	1	7
DM27	1	7
IR8608-75-3-1-3	1	7
IR29	1	7
B4069C-Sm-162-2-1	1	9
B414c-Sm-162-2-1	1	9
Chianung Sen Yu 28	1	9
IR25588-32-2	1	5
IR26621-105-2-1-2	1	5
IR9782-111-2-1-2	1	7
IR9852-22-3	1	7
Nanjing 22-3	1	9
R22-2	1	9
SI-PI-682144	1	7
SI-PI-693033	1	5
SI-PI-692106	1	9
Suweon 294	1	5
TNAU633	1	9
UPR254-24-1	1	7
UPR79-106	1	5
BR160-2B-4-8-HR16	0	5
PNA237-F4-130-1	1	5
PNA237F4223-1	3	7
RP1890-418-241	1	7
BG276-5	1	3
DR83 (IR2053-261-2-3)	1	3
Sind Basmati (Latefy)	3	9
IR6	1	9
IET4094 (DR82)	1	7

using the 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice. Basmati 370, the susceptible check, developed 37.8% deadhearts and 60% whiteheads.

Only IR13639-34, BG276-5, and DR83 were moderately resistant (see table). Varieties were more susceptible to whiteheads than to deadhearts. □

Field screening for resistance to leafhopper (LF)

R. Velusamy, postdoctoral fellow, Entomology Department, IRRI; and S. Chelliah, professor of entomology, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003, India

LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* is a serious rice pest in Tamil Nadu, particularly after high N application. We developed a field screening technique to evaluate rices for LF resistance.

Fields were bordered by coconut trees and partly shaded. A basal application of 60-26-41 kg NPK/ha was incorporated before planting. Five border rows of susceptible CO 36 were planted at 20- × 60-cm spacing. Alternate 5-m-long rows of test entries and CO 36 were planted at 10 cm between-plant spacing. One row of resistant TKM6 was included in each replication. Fifteen days after planting, phorate granules at 1.0 kg ai/ha were applied to the susceptible border rows. The experiment was in a randomized block design with five replications.

Reactions of rice accessions to LF infestation in the field, Coimbatore, India.

Accession	Damage rating ^a
ARC6650	1 a
ARC10550	1 a
Ptb 33	1 a
TKM6	1 a
IR4707-106-3-2	3 a
Muthumanikam	3 a
W1263	3 a
V. P. Samba	3 a
GEB24	3 a
T7	3 a
CO 36	9 b

^a Means of 5 replications. Means followed by a common letter are not statistically different at 5% level by DMRT.

Sixty kg N/ha in split doses was applied to induce LF infestation. When the CO 36 had at least 50% infested leaves, test entries were rated on a 1-9 scale (see table).

Applying phorate granules induced 100% LF infestation in CO 36. Utilizing ARC10550, IR4707-106-3-2, Muthumanikam, V. P. samba, and T7 as donors, breeding lines with LF resistance were developed at Coimbatore and are being evaluated at different centers. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization ADVERSE SOILS TOLERANCE

Performance of rice genotypes in coastal saline soils

T. S. Sinha and A. K. Bandyopadhyay, Central Soil Salinity Research Institute, Regional Research Station Canning, Canning Town, 24 Parganas, West Bengal 743329, India

Rice genotypes traditionally grown in coastal saline soils may have poor yield potential but may contain valuable genes for salinity tolerance.

We evaluated 23 genotypes collected from coastal saline areas of Balasore and Puri districts, Orissa, for salt toler-

ance and grain yield in Jun-Nov. In 1982, 23 genotypes and the local check CSR6 were transplanted in a randomized complete block design with 3 replications. The mean ECe at transplanting was 9.7 dS/m and that of standing water (15 cm) 4.4 dS/m. At flowering, salinity of soil at 15 cm ranged from 6.7 to 9.3 dS/m.

Plant survival ranged from 53% for Ratnachuri to 98% for CSR6. Survival of Patini, Katkichandi, Patnai, Velki, and Valuki was similar to that of CSR6. Spikelet sterility, a common problem in saline soils, ranged from 14.5 (CSR6) to 50.4% (Pakhira). Velki (15.0%), Valuki (15.9%), and Patini (16.5%) had